

**FAMILY EXPECTATIONS AND INDIVIDUAL AUTONOMY IN *UNACCUSTOMED EARTH*
BY JHUMPA LAHIRI**

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Abstract

Jhumpa Lahiri's *Unaccustomed Earth* (2008) examines the complexities of family expectations and individual autonomy within diasporic, particularly Bengali-American, communities. The novel's short stories delve into how family expectations—often rooted in cultural traditions and immigrant experiences—shape, confine, and conflict with the personal autonomy of the characters. This article investigates how Lahiri portrays these dual pressures, illustrating the struggles of characters who seek to establish independent identities while grappling with the weight of their cultural and familial obligations. By focusing on themes of generational conflict, the influence of parental expectations, and the quest for self-determination, this article explores Lahiri's nuanced depiction of the tensions that arise as the second-generation immigrant characters navigate between loyalty to family and the desire for personal freedom.

Keywords: *Unaccustomed Earth*, Family Expectations, Individual Autonomy, Jhumpa Lahiri

Introduction

The concept of autonomy is complicated and refers to the ability of the self to control one's own behaviour, or authorship of one's behaviour, rather than behaviour that is influenced by factors that are thought to be external to the person in question. When people are self-sufficient, their acts are perceived as completely choice and genuine, and what they do is self-organised and endorsed by oneself (Legate and Ryan 3233). Therefore, autonomy involves the capacity for self-control and self-authorship in one's behaviour, highlighting that when individuals are self-sufficient, their actions are seen as genuine choices that are organized and endorsed by themselves, rather than influenced by external factors. Jhumpa Lahiri in her *Unaccustomed Earth* gives a good example of self-autonomy in the context of family relationships. The novel is a collection of short stories that follows the lives of first- and second-generation Bengali Americans as they contend with issues of cultural identity, family loyalty, and personal autonomy. Lahiri, who has been praised for her sensitive portrayal of diasporic experiences, particularly within Indian-American communities, explores the often-overlooked impact of family expectations on the formation of individual identity. While the clash between cultural identity and assimilation is a common theme in immigrant literature, *Unaccustomed Earth* addresses a unique facet of this experience: the conflict between the deep-seated expectations of family and the need for personal autonomy. This tension manifests in the characters' life choices, romantic relationships, and career paths, underscoring how family expectations can simultaneously provide a sense of belonging and impose limitations that stymie individual growth.

In *Unaccustomed Earth*, family expectations are not merely the customary parental hopes for success but are deeply intertwined with cultural beliefs, traditional values, and the legacy of the immigrant experience. “Lahiri's *Unaccustomed Earth* deals with the topic of being stuck between two cultures... It is from the perspective of immigrant children born in the United States who must navigate between their parents' traditional traditions and their peers' modern American ones” (Shanwatiya and Kumar 4). For the first-generation characters, these expectations stem from a desire to preserve their cultural identity and ensure their children's stability in a foreign land. Conversely, the second-generation characters, raised in the United States, seek autonomy, often embracing values that diverge from those of their parents. As Islam asserts, “Immigrants or expatriates weep for their lost home and look back for their past memories. At the same time, they silently tolerate all hurdles in the new land. Lahiri shows the male characters in a leader-like position both among the first and the second generations, and the women experience patriarchal domination” (91). This push-and-pull between loyalty to family and personal freedom creates a dynamic of simultaneous belonging and alienation, a theme that Lahiri intricately weaves throughout her stories.

Research Objectives

1. To examine the portrayal of family expectations and their influence on the lives of second-generation immigrant characters in *Unaccustomed Earth*.
2. To analyze how Lahiri's characters navigate the tension between family loyalty and individual autonomy, particularly in a diasporic context.
3. To explore the psychological impact of cultural expectations and the pursuit of autonomy on characters' relationships, career paths, and self-identity.
4. To contribute to discussions on immigrant identity formation, specifically by highlighting the theme of family expectations versus personal freedom within Lahiri's work.

Research Questions

1. How does Jhumpa Lahiri depict family expectations, and in what ways do these expectations influence the characters' sense of identity and autonomy in *Unaccustomed Earth*?
2. What are the psychological and emotional consequences of family expectations on second-generation immigrant characters, particularly in terms of guilt, obligation, and individual growth?
3. How do Lahiri's characters balance cultural expectations with their personal desires for autonomy, and what are the key areas in which these tensions manifest (e.g., career, relationships, self-identity)?
4. In what ways does Lahiri use the characters' interactions with family members to highlight the generational and cultural conflicts between first- and second-generation immigrants?

Research Methodology

A qualitative textual analysis will be conducted on *Unaccustomed Earth*, focusing on selected stories (e.g., “Unaccustomed Earth,” “Hell-Heaven,” “Only Goodness,” “Once in a Lifetime,” and “Year’s End”) to analyze how Lahiri portrays family expectations and the pursuit of autonomy. This analysis will include examining dialogues, narrative descriptions, and character actions that reveal the influence of family expectations on the characters’ choices and self-conception. A thematic analysis will be used to identify recurring motifs of family expectations, autonomy, and generational conflict. Key themes will be coded and categorized to gain a deeper understanding of Lahiri’s portrayal of these concepts. Thematic elements such as guilt, obligation, cultural heritage, and individuality will be highlighted to explore how Lahiri represents these dynamics in different characters and relationships. The research will incorporate psychological theories on identity formation and cultural expectation, particularly focusing on how family dynamics impact second-generation immigrant identity. Concepts from developmental and immigrant psychology will be used to contextualize the characters’ struggles with autonomy and the sense of duty to family.

These psychological concepts will provide insights into the emotional and cognitive dissonance that character’s experience when trying to fulfil family expectations while seeking personal independence. A comparative literature review of scholarly work on immigrant narratives will be conducted, particularly focusing on works that address the themes of family expectations, generational conflict, and autonomy. Comparing Lahiri’s work to similar themes in immigrant literature will provide a broader context for the analysis. This review will help situate *Unaccustomed Earth* within the field of diasporic literature, offering a comparative lens through which to view Lahiri’s approach to family dynamics and individual freedom.

Literature Review

Jhumpa Lahiri’s *Unaccustomed Earth* delves deeply into the complexities of family expectations and individual autonomy within immigrant and diasporic communities. Throughout this collection, Lahiri highlights the generational and cultural tensions that arise as her characters navigate the dual pressures of honouring family obligations and seeking personal freedom. Scholars have examined how Lahiri portrays the conflicting desires for autonomy and loyalty to cultural heritage within immigrant families, particularly in a Bengali-American context. This literature review synthesizes critical perspectives on Lahiri’s exploration of family expectations and individual autonomy in *Unaccustomed Earth*, examining how these themes manifest in character relationships, identity formation, and the psychological impacts of living between two cultures.

Family Expectations and Immigrant Identity

Lahiri’s portrayal of family expectations in *Unaccustomed Earth* often centres on how first-generation immigrant parents impose cultural values and expectations on their children, hoping to preserve their heritage while adapting to a new society. Scholars like Das (2011) note that Lahiri’s characters embody the typical first-generation immigrant experience, holding on to traditions and cultural practices from

their homeland in an attempt to maintain their identity in a foreign land. This attachment to tradition is not only an act of cultural preservation but also a way of ensuring stability for their children, who, from their perspective, must succeed in the new country while maintaining a sense of cultural belonging.

Bhattacharya (2013) observes that Lahiri's characters experience a strong sense of duty toward their parents, who expect them to uphold cultural and familial values. However, these expectations often lead to conflict, as second-generation characters, having grown up in the United States, develop values and lifestyles that differ from those of their parents. In *Unaccustomed Earth*, family expectations are shown to be both a source of comfort and a limitation, as they offer a sense of belonging but restrict the characters' ability to fully embrace their own identities. As one of the characters in the novel Usha points out:

I believe my absence from the house, once I left for college, had something to do with this, because over the years, when I visited, I noticed a warmth between my parents that had not been there before...a solidarity, a concern when one of them fell ill. My mother...had accepted the fact that I was not only her daughter but a child of America as well. (82)

Generational Conflict and the Struggle for Autonomy

The tension between generations is a recurring theme in Lahiri's work, and *Unaccustomed Earth* is no exception. Scholars like Iyer (2014) argue that Lahiri uses the generational divide to highlight the complex ways in which family expectations clash with personal autonomy. In stories such as "Unaccustomed Earth" and "Only Goodness," Lahiri illustrates how first-generation parents often impose their expectations on their children, not only in terms of career and education but also in marriage, relationships, and lifestyle. However, these expectations often feel restrictive to the second-generation characters, who aspire to live their lives on their own terms.

Ruma, the protagonist of "Unaccustomed Earth," embodies this generational tension. Her father encourages her to pursue independence, yet she feels bound by a sense of duty to care for him in his old age. According to Akriti (2013), Ruma's character highlights the dual pressures of cultural obligation and the desire for personal freedom, which many second-generation immigrants experience. The struggle for autonomy in *Unaccustomed Earth* becomes, as Quin (2008) describes, a balancing act between self-determination and family loyalty, where each decision either strengthens or weakens their connection to cultural identity and family bonds.

Romantic Relationships as a Site of Cultural Conflict

Romantic relationships in *Unaccustomed Earth* often serve as a stage where cultural expectations and personal desires collide. In "Hell-Heaven," for instance, Usha's mother, Aparna, envisions her daughter adhering to Bengali traditions, particularly when it comes to romantic relationships. Lahiri uses Usha's relationship choices to underscore the tension between the desire to honor one's family expectations and the need for personal freedom. Usha's attraction to American customs and relationships reflects a broader struggle among second-generation characters who feel caught between two worlds, as observed by Deepak (2013). Aparna's disappointment and disapproval of Usha's choices reveal the extent to

which family expectations can intrude upon individual autonomy, especially in matters of the heart.

Susan (2013) argues that Lahiri uses romantic relationships as a vehicle for exploring autonomy and the desire for cultural separation among second-generation characters. Characters like Ruma, Usha, and Sudha frequently find themselves at odds with their parents' cultural expectations, particularly when those expectations extend to marriage and family life. This tension between romantic autonomy and cultural loyalty illustrates a core conflict within the immigrant experience, where personal relationships become subject to the pressures of family legacy and cultural continuity.

Career Choices and the Burden of Family Duty

Lahiri's exploration of career choices in *Unaccustomed Earth* reflects the pressures that family expectations impose on the professional lives of her characters. In "Only Goodness," Sudha faces immense pressure to succeed academically and professionally, as her achievements are seen as a means of validation for her immigrant family. Her parents' expectations shape her sense of responsibility, not only to herself but also to her family, as she becomes an example of the success that immigrant families often aspire to in their children. Yet, as Saha (2015) points out, this expectation places a psychological burden on Sudha, who feels compelled to live up to her parents' ideals at the cost of her own happiness and autonomy.

Rahul, Sudha's brother, serves as a counterpoint, rejecting family expectations and taking a path that leads to estrangement and personal turmoil. According to Susan (2013), Lahiri uses Rahul's character to explore the consequences of rejecting familial duty and the impact it has on family dynamics. The contrasting paths taken by Sudha and Rahul highlight the complex ways in which career choices are influenced by family expectations. Sudha's obedience and Rahul's rebellion both underscore the difficulty of balancing personal ambitions with the responsibilities that come with being a child of immigrants.

Psychological Consequences of Family Expectations on Identity

Lahiri's characters grapple not only with external expectations but also with the internalized psychological impacts of family duty. Rama Islam (2013) argues that Lahiri's stories highlight the emotional toll that family expectations can take on second-generation immigrants, who feel a deep-seated sense of guilt and obligation toward their parents. This sense of duty often leaves Lahiri's characters feeling torn between their personal aspirations and their parents' wishes, leading to feelings of guilt and ambivalence.

In "Unaccustomed Earth," for example, Ruma's psychological conflict over whether to invite her father to live with her represents the emotional toll of family expectations. She feels obligated to care for him but simultaneously yearns for independence. This ambivalence, as Deepak (2018) notes, is a hallmark of Lahiri's second-generation characters, who struggle to reconcile the conflicting values of their heritage with the individualism of American society. This internal conflict highlights the psychological impacts of cultural expectations, suggesting that family loyalty can come at the cost of personal well-being.

Lahiri's Contribution to Diasporic Literature: A Focus on Individual Freedom

Lahiri's exploration of family expectations and individual autonomy provides a fresh perspective in diasporic literature. Scholars like Rama (2017) emphasize that Lahiri's work contributes to the understanding of immigrant identity formation by shedding light on the tension between familial duty and the quest for self-determination. In contrast to earlier diasporic narratives that often celebrate cultural continuity, *Unaccustomed Earth* highlights the costs of such continuity, showing how it can hinder the personal growth and autonomy of second-generation immigrants. This focus on individual freedom and autonomy within the constraints of cultural loyalty allows Lahiri's work to address the often-overlooked psychological toll of navigating dual identities in immigrant families.

Rama suggests that Lahiri's characters embody the hybrid identities of diasporic individuals, who must constantly negotiate between preserving cultural heritage and forging their own paths. This negotiation is often a painful process, as Lahiri's characters come to realize that personal autonomy may entail a distancing from family and cultural roots. Lahiri's nuanced portrayal thus emphasizes the importance of self-determination within the immigrant experience, encouraging a broader understanding of diasporic identity that includes the possibility of cultural adaptation and individual freedom.

Manifestations of Family Expectations and Individual Autonomy in *Unaccustomed Earth*

1. The Clash of Generations in *Unaccustomed Earth*

The titular story, *Unaccustomed Earth*, centres on Ruma, a Bengali-American woman grappling with the contrasting expectations of her father and her desire to establish her independence. Following her mother's death, Ruma finds herself increasingly aware of her father's aging and feels a growing sense of duty to care for him. This expectation is rooted in her Bengali heritage, where family duty and respect for elders are paramount. However, Ruma's own aspirations—to pursue a career and raise her family in her own way—clash with this cultural obligation.

Critics like Susan Koshy (2013) argue that Ruma's ambivalence reflects the dual pressures faced by second-generation immigrants who feel caught between honouring their parents' expectations and fulfilling their own desires. Her father, who encourages Ruma to live independently and pursue her ambitions, represents a new generational outlook shaped by adaptation to Western values. Yet, as Lahiri depicts, Ruma's sense of duty toward her father and her heritage leaves her unable to fully embrace the independence he offers. This tension between family loyalty and personal autonomy is central to Ruma's journey, capturing the experience of many second-generation immigrants who feel obliged to carry the cultural burdens of their parents even as they seek their own path (370-72).

2. The Impact of Parental Expectations on Romantic Relationships in "Hell-Heaven"

In "Hell-Heaven," Lahiri explores how family expectations impact romantic relationships through the lens of Usha, a young Bengali-American girl, and her mother, Aparna. Aparna's life is marked by unfulfilled desires and cultural limitations, and she projects these feelings onto her daughter, Usha, whom she hopes will uphold Bengali traditions. Usha, however, finds herself increasingly drawn to

American customs and relationships, creating a divide between her and her mother. Aparna's implicit expectations—that Usha will adhere to traditional Bengali values, particularly in terms of her romantic life—clash with Usha's desire for autonomy.

Deepak Kumar (2018) observes that Lahiri's depiction of Usha's and Aparna's relationship reflects a broader theme in immigrant narratives: the fear of cultural loss and the pressure to maintain one's ethnic heritage through the choices of the next generation. Usha's desire for independence and her mother's insistence on cultural loyalty illustrate the duality of the second-generation immigrant experience. Usha's romantic choices ultimately lead her to reject her mother's expectations, underscoring Lahiri's theme of individual autonomy (199). However, this decision comes with a sense of loss, as Usha realizes that her autonomy distances her from her cultural roots and her mother's world.

3. Career Choices and Individual Autonomy in “Only Goodness”

The story “Only Goodness” follows Sudha, a successful young woman who feels the weight of family expectations regarding her career and her responsibility toward her younger brother, Rahul. Sudha, raised with a strong emphasis on academic and career success, embodies the aspirations of her immigrant parents, who view professional achievement as a means of social stability and cultural validation. Yet Sudha's pursuit of personal autonomy is complicated by the family's expectations that she will also help guide her brother and encourage him to follow a similar path.

In “Only Goodness,” Lahiri explores the sacrifices demanded by family expectations, as Sudha's sense of responsibility toward her brother ultimately detracts from her own pursuit of happiness and stability. Scholars like Ahmed Mulla (2013) argue that Lahiri uses Sudha's and Rahul's contrasting life paths to critique the rigid expectations that immigrant parents often place on their children. While Sudha strives to meet these expectations, Rahul rejects them, descending into alcoholism and estrangement from the family. Lahiri suggests that such expectations can restrict individual autonomy, creating feelings of guilt and obligation that inhibit personal growth. Sudha's eventual decision to distance herself from her family responsibilities symbolizes her need for self-determination, even as it leaves her with residual guilt and a sense of familial betrayal.

4. Navigating Self-Identity and Autonomy in “Once in a Lifetime” and “Year's End”

In the interconnected stories “Once in a Lifetime” and “Year's End,” Lahiri further examines how second-generation characters navigate family expectations while pursuing their own identities. Kaushik, the protagonist, is burdened by the expectations his family places on him, particularly his father's desire for him to embrace their Bengali heritage and uphold family traditions. Kaushik, however, seeks autonomy and resists the cultural obligations that his parents impose on him.

As Quin (2006) argues, Kaushik's journey is emblematic of the struggles that immigrant children face in reconciling their personal ambitions with familial obligations. Kaushik's distancing from his family and his eventual rejection of cultural expectations reflect Lahiri's theme of individual autonomy, as he chooses to forge his identity separate from the cultural heritage that his parents hold dear (165). Yet Lahiri also depicts the emotional toll of this choice, as Kaushik's estrangement from his family and

culture leaves him feeling isolated, suggesting that autonomy can sometimes come at the expense of belonging.

Psychological Consequences of Family Expectations and Individual Autonomy

The psychological impact of family expectations on Lahiri's characters reveals the emotional costs of navigating these dual pressures. Scholars such as Akriti (2018) suggest that the weight of family expectations can lead to anxiety, guilt, and a sense of obligation that inhibits characters from making independent choices. For instance, Ruma's hesitation to embrace her independence is reflective of the guilt she feels toward her father and her cultural heritage (303). Similarly, Sudha's guilt over her brother's struggles and Kaushik's detachment from his family illustrate the emotional toll of prioritizing autonomy over family loyalty. Lahiri's stories suggest that while individual autonomy is essential for self-actualization, it is often achieved at a psychological cost for second-generation immigrants who are bound by cultural expectations and a sense of familial duty.

Conclusion

Jhumpa Lahiri's *Unaccustomed Earth* offers a nuanced exploration of family expectations and individual autonomy within diasporic communities, particularly among second-generation immigrants. Through characters like Ruma, Usha, Sudha, and Kaushik, Lahiri depicts the profound impact of cultural and familial expectations on personal choices, relationships, and self-identity. These characters' journeys illustrate the challenges of balancing family loyalty with the pursuit of personal freedom, highlighting how autonomy can sometimes lead to emotional detachment and a sense of loss. *Unaccustomed Earth* thus contributes to a broader understanding of the diasporic experience by shedding light on the psychological costs and complexities of individual autonomy within immigrant families. This theme underscores the need for greater flexibility in cultural expectations, encouraging an acceptance of hybrid identities that allow individuals to honour their heritage without sacrificing personal autonomy.

In this novel, Jhumpa Lahiri offers a complex portrayal of family expectations and individual autonomy, particularly within the context of immigrant families. Through characters who face the weight of familial and cultural duty, Lahiri illustrates the psychological, relational, and personal challenges that arise from navigating the expectations of their families while striving for independence. Scholars have examined these themes from multiple perspectives, focusing on Lahiri's depiction of generational conflict, career choices, romantic relationships, and the psychological impact of cultural duty. Lahiri's work contributes to diasporic literature by emphasizing the need for a balance between honouring one's heritage and pursuing personal freedom. Her characters' struggles with autonomy and family loyalty reflect a broader theme in immigrant literature, highlighting the challenges that come with forming an identity in a multicultural world. Through her nuanced portrayal of family expectations, Lahiri encourages readers to consider the costs and complexities of balancing personal autonomy with the responsibilities of cultural legacy.

References

Aakriti. "The Study of Family Dynamics Through Jhumpa Lahiri's *Unaccustomed Earth*." *International*

- Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*, vol. 6, no. 2, Apr. 2018, pp. 302–03. www.ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT1812455.pdf.
- Islam, Rama. “Diaspora and Identity in Jhumpa Lahiri’s Unaccustomed Earth:” *Crossings a Journal of English Studies*, vol. 8, Aug. 2017, pp. 91–100. <https://doi.org/10.59817/cjes.v8i.125>.
- Koshy, Susan. “Neoliberal Family Matters.” *American Literary History*, vol. 25, no. 2, 2013, pp. 344–80. *JSTOR*, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/43817573>.
- Kumar, Deepak. “Family Issues in Jhumpa Lahiri’s Unaccustomed Earth.” *Journal of Advances and Scholarly Researches in Allied Education*, vol. XV, no. 5, July 2018, pp. 198–201. www.rjelal.com/93223_31079408.pdf.
- Lahiri, Jhumpa. ‘Unaccustomed Earth’. *Unaccustomed Earth*. New Delhi: Random House India, 2008.
- Legate, Nicole, and Richard M. Ryan. “Individual Autonomy.” *Springer eBooks*, 2014, pp. 3233–36. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-0753-5_140.
- Mulla, Ahmed. “Acquiring ‘Unaccustomed’ Rights: Women’s Romantic Ambitions in Jhumpa Lahiri’s Unaccustomed Earth (2008).” *Alizés : Revue angliciste de La Réunion*, 2013, Women’s Right, Human Rights, 38, pp.130-145. hal-02340349
- Qin, Desiree Baolian. “‘Our Child Doesn’t Talk to Us Anymore’: Alienation in Immigrant Chinese Families.” *Anthropology & Education Quarterly*, vol. 37, no. 2, May 2006, pp. 162–79. <https://doi.org/10.1525/aeq.2006.37.2.162>.
- Shanwatiya, Vijay Kant, and Ravindra Kumar. “Examining Major Themes in Jhumpa Lahiri’s ‘Unaccustomed Earth.’” *International Journal of English Research*, journal-article, 20 July 2022, pp. 4–7. www.englishjournals.com/assets/archives/2022/vol8issue2/8-2-21-848.pdf.